

**Physicochemical Examination of Krishna
River and Canal Waters in Nalgonda,
Krishna and Guntur Districts of
Andhra Pradesh**

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THE river and its tributaries flow in a region embracing large areas of industrial and agricultural activities pointing to the possible sources of contamination. Lack of study prompted the authors to collect baseline data of surface waters pertaining to the river Krishna and its canals flowing through Nalgonda, Krishna and Guntur districts of Andhra Pradesh. Four stations were selected at approximately equidistant places over a length of 200 km (Fig. 1) from the shore to the inner part of the river. The fifth station was selected on the branch canal (Buckingham canal) of the river which departs from the main stream at Vijayawada.

Experimental

Monthly samples were collected at different stations with equal intervals from July 1986 to June 1988, during daytime at a distance of about 3 m inside the river from the bank and at a depth of 30–60 cm. The water samples were characterised in terms of parameters like temperature, dissolved oxygen, silicates, pH, total hardness and chlorides. The monthly studies were classified into pre-monsoon (March to June), monsoon (July to October) and post-monsoon (November to February) seasons considering the available meteorological data.

An Eltop 3020 digital pH-meter and a Carl-Zeiss Spekol spectrophotometer with 0.995 cm corex cells were used. All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Results and Discussion

A polyethylene vessel (20 dm³) was dipped into the surface waters at the sampling spot. The temperatures of water samples varied in the range 27–33°. Elevated temperatures at late pre-monsoon months (April/May) and late post-monsoon month (February) in both years were noticed. It has been reported that photosynthetic activity and concurrent algal growth are temperature dependent² while the duration of sunshine and temperature also influence the productivity³. Separate samples were collected for dissolved oxygen (DO) analysis⁴.

DO in these waters varied from 7.5 to 11.5 mg dm⁻³. In general, high values were observed in monsoon season both at Mattapalli and Vijayawada stations. There was a general trend of increase in DO concentration as the distance between stations and sea-cost decreases. The observed decrease at Vijayawada may be attributed to the excessive inputs emerged from municipal wastes of Vijayawada city causing oxygen depletion. Further, Sangam Jagarlamudi being an enclosed canal with no inflow or outflow of water causes stagnatic conditions leading to depletion of oxygen experiences a low DO content. The high DO content was observed during monsoon season because the fast moving river water absorbs more atmospheric oxygen. The two other DO maxima observed in pre-monsoon and post-monsoon seasons are due to the environmental conditions suitable for phytoplankton production as reported earlier⁵. However, in the present studies the DO reached its maximum in summer months due to increase of temperature which accelerates the photosynthetic oxygen production by phytoplankton as reported elsewhere^{1,6}.

Silicates were estimated colorimetrically using molybdenum blue method⁷. The silicates varied in the range 11–18 mg dm⁻³. The lowest silicate content was observed in the surface waters at Vijayawada and at Srikakulam in April 1987 and in January 1988 (i.e. low-flow period) respectively, while the highest value was noticed at Mattapalli

Fig. 1. The Krishna river - location of stations.

and Sangam Jagarlamudi in July 1987 (i.e. high-flow period). High values of silicates were recorded both in pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons and are mainly attributed to the river runoff. The observed low values during April 1987 indicates the biological utilisation of silicates for the formation of diatoms during post-monsoon season. The same trend was reported by other workers⁸. As we move from Mattapalli to sea-coast, the silicate concentration decreases in pre-monsoon and post-monsoon seasons. A reverse trend is observed in monsoon season which may be due to the erosion of soils and rocks due to high-flow conditions prevailing.

In general, pH of the waters varied between 7 and 8.5 during the study period. The variation of pH with distance from Mattapalli to sea coast clearly indicates an increasing trend in all seasons. The values at Vijayawada in pre-monsoon season may be due to the absence of runoff and stagnant conditions in summer season. Low pH values were recorded in monsoon season at all stations due to the acidic nature of rain-water.

Total hardness was estimated complexometrically⁹. The results were computed in equivalents of CaCO_3 , mg dm^{-3} . As we traverse from the interior point to sea-end, there is a general trend of increase in hardness. The hardness reflects the

nature of geological formations with which the water is in contact.

Mohr's method¹⁰ was adopted for the estimation of chlorides. The values of chlorides were found to be in the range $30-52 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$. Lowest chlorides values were observed at Mattapalli (October 1986), Amaravathi (December 1986) and Vijayawada (March 1987) while the highest value was recorded at Mattapalli in May 1988. The high content of chloride during April/May at Mattapalli (which is a pilgrimage place) was due to the artificial chlorination, i.e. spreading of bleaching powder during that period.

The detailed distribution studies of the above parameters in the five stations show more or less the same trends which indicate that these parameters are associated with the existing environmental conditions.

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NOTES

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